

Playing Through Water: Solastalgia and Environmental Imagination in Post-Flood Digital Worlds

Digital games rarely offer straightforward lessons about climate crisis, but they can mediate how we encounter and process environmental loss. This paper argues that post-flood games—Submerged (Uppercut Games, 2015), Raft (Redbeet Interactive, 2022), and FAR: Changing Tides (Okomotive, 2022)—do not simply simulate catastrophe; instead, they immerse players in ambiguous, waterlogged worlds where uncertainty, vulnerability, and open-ended adaptation become the core experience. These games refuse both restoration fantasies and managerial control, instead cultivating an affective space for engaging with environmental loss and the challenges of an unsettled world.

In sharp contrast, Anno 2070 (Ubisoft, 2011) operationalizes ecological catastrophe as a system to be managed, foregrounding optimization, control, and techno-utopian problem-solving. This juxtaposition reveals a fundamental tension in digital environmental narratives: between what Glenn Albrecht calls solastalgia—the distress of environmental loss—and the blue humanities' call to rethink our relationship with water, ambiguities, and more-than-human worlds.

I conclude with Terra Nil (Free Lives, 2023), a city-building game which radicalizes the genre by centering ecological restoration and the erasure of human impact, offering a provocative alternative that invites players to envision repair without a return to business as usual. By analyzing the affective and procedural dimensions of these post-flood games through the lenses of affect theory, blue ecocriticism, and environmental psychology, this paper contributes to ecocritical debates about the role of digital media in shaping our emotional and imaginative responses to environmental crisis, and the possibilities for cultivating new forms of ecological imagination and responsibility.

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